

A table summarizing the responses of the managerial participants (Follow-up study)

No.	Mock name	Country	Position	Business area	Do you have any measurements about the perception of the workplace?	Do you have any measurements about the perception of the RPA solutions used in the company?	If you do, how does it work?
1	Harald	Finland	department manager	accounting	Yes	No	Annual survey + team meetings + action plan
2	Karla	Lithuania	transition manager	finance	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
3	Ryszard	Poland	project manager	groupsupport	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
4	Steven	Germany	sales manager	finance	No	No	Nothing
5	Alexandra	Finland	team manager	accounting	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
6	Adrianna	Poland	department manager	IT	Yes	No	Annual survey + team meetings + action plan
7	Finland	Poland	project manager	IT	Yes	No	Annual survey + team meetings + action plan
8	Kamila	Poland	service manager	accounting	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
9	Mikael	Germany	service manager	finance	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
10	Milenna	Sweden	team manager	accounting	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
11	Vera	Finland	department manager	payroll	Yes	No	Annual survey + individual meetings
12	Ulrika	Sweden	project manager	accounting	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
13	Tadeusz	Lithuania	service manager	payroll	Yes	No	Annual survey + team meetings + action plan
14	María	Lithuania	process expert	IT	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
15	Alan	Poland	service manager	accounting	Yes	No	Annual survey + team meetings + action plan
16	Daria	Poland	process expert	payroll	Yes	No	Annual survey + team meetings + action plan
17	Janette	Poland	process expert	finance	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
18	Henrikka	Finland	service manager	IT	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
19	Nicolas	Norway	project manager	finance	Yes	No	Annual survey + action plan
20	Waldemar	Poland	sales manager	accounting	Yes	No	Quarterly survey, no followup

Appendix 1. Scenario used in the research.

Ladies and Gentlemen,

Please read the information about the new program called *Future Craft*, which is based on Robotic Process Automation and Autonomous Artificial Intelligence. It is extremely important that you read the *Future Craft* product description and think about its use in your company. Below we present its main functionalities. Please read them carefully, and then respond to set of questions.

Software's description:

Future Craft is a new global provider of Robotic Process Automation (RPA) technology. RPA is a type of computer program that provides a digital workforce designed to automate complex, end-to-end operational processes.

RPA provides not only the automation of business processes to reduce the time of manual processing. Your enterprise needs a Digital Workforce to cope with rapid market changes. Our solutions have elements of artificial intelligence, which is why they have wide possibilities and can help your organization cope with digital challenges, and develop faster, wider and more agile. A completely new functionality is allowing the system to make autonomous decisions in selected cases (for instance: buying some product when artificial intelligence detects some shortage after the process analysis), provided that employees agree to this decision-making independence.

We believe in using the transformative power of automation to unleash infinite human potential. With the help of our platform, you can empower people to automate their boring work, which will free them from wasting time and allow them to devote themselves to creative tasks that add value to your organization.

Main advantages:

- provides a 24/7 digital workforce
- allows you to get instant access to the resources of a digital workforce that is integrated with built-in artificial intelligence skills
- virtual workers are smart and use machine learning to develop
- the program allows the automation of some tasks by the users themselves, without prior programming experience